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Addressing retention at an English-medium Engineering College: A case study of Freshman students in the Middle East

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ABSTRACT

The low student retention rate in an English medium engineering college in the Middle East has been attributed to the students' lack of readiness in language and sciences, lack of motivation, and issues regarding adjusting to university life. To address this, a new freshman course called Introduction to Engineering, ENGR110 was introduced in 2015. The course, incorporated into the First Year Experience (FYE) program, was designed to introduce students to the different majors offered, soft skills such as team work, time management, goal setting, problem-solving, and to establish a learning community on campus. It includes hands-on activities, problem-solving sessions, seminars/workshops, field trips as well as presentations by alumni. A particular emphasis on having students make informed decisions early about their choice of major was seen as critical in getting students focused and motivated. This paper

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describes the impact that the course has had on student retention based on students' to two consecutive surveys.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: first-year experience (FYE), retention, learner-centered teaching

INTRODUCTION

Success in student retention reflects the effectiveness of education students seek to acquire [1] and figures have implications on both the finances and the reputation of colleges and universities [1, 2]. Since the 1980's, in engineering colleges "difficulty of the subject and the mismatching of student and academic expectations, have resulted in higher dropout rates than for many other subjects" [3]. Providing students with additional support and applying teaching strategies in the first year of engineering are solutions provided by engineering colleges, as traditionally taught courses have been criticised for being overly academic and not providing enough knowledge of engineering as a career [1]. In the Arabian Gulf region where the current study has been initiated, the higher education (HE) system was primarily established in the 1990's and early 2000's.

Due to the relatively young age of the system, attention to student retention has thus become of more relevance in recent years. Also, there is evidence of students frequently requesting to change majors during their course, often multiple times. According to Freedman [4] this is not uncommon, but high rates result in a considerable waste of resources and time, for faculty, students and institution. This paper describes the initial phase of a longitudinal study on the effects of a new, introductory course Introduction to Engineering (ENGR110), which aims at both decreasing the rate of changes in majors and at improving student retention. The course was implemented for a cohort of approximately 150 female and 60 male first-year undergraduate students. The course outcomes were then evaluated via two student surveys and through the assessment of Student Learning Outcomes (SLO's).

1 MAIN FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENT RETENTION

The two principal aspects affecting student retention are the students' approaches to HE and approaches implemented by HE institutes to improve retention. Students' approaches to HE are affected by their school experiences, their family background, by the way in which education is viewed in their culture and by the students' prior knowledge regarding HE [5, 6]. A review of the literature pertaining specifically to engineering students' retention [1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9] showed that engineering colleges and institutes of HE have attempted to respond to the students' needs mentioned above. According to the research, the following five approaches are the most common ones intended to improve retention; high entry criteria [1, 2], providing support mechanisms, including helping students to improve their study skills, instructor and peer mentoring and advising, as well as "preparation, transition programming [and] first year experience (FYE) programming," [2 p.2].

Another way is to keep students in cohorts throughout their freshman year [7]. Activities which students appreciated, according to Willis [6], were interactive learning experiences, including field trips, laboratory work, site visits and design projects, as well as work placement, which help students to adjust and integrate into HE. These

involve active learning and group work, important motivators to engineering students [7]. Such active learning and problem-based learning (PBL) methods also promote the general criteria for learning outcomes provided by the Accreditation Board of Engineering and Technology (ABET) [10]. Furthermore, actual first year engineering courses help students to “feel more confident in their engineering skills and more deeply integrated into their engineering careers and therefore more likely to remain in engineering,” [1 p.10].

1.1 Retention issues pertinent to the current study

In the current study, which took place in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), some young men and women face specific hurdles in secondary and higher education. These include parental disinterest, poor academic preparation for higher education [11], poor English language skills obtained at school and a lack of career counselling in high school [12]. Over 70% of students in HE in the UAE are women [12], perhaps because they are already performing better than male students in secondary education [13], as well as at tertiary level [14].

Moreover, males have the advantage of joining the military, police or government jobs as alternatives to pursuing higher education [12]. The engineering college where the current takes place is sponsored by a major Emirati oil company, and its international partners and all undergraduate students have signed an agreement to work for the company. Therefore, students are guaranteed a job on entry to HE. Currently, 1547 undergraduate and 650 graduate students are enrolled at the college.

1.2 Existing support system: The first year experience

The First Year Experience (FYE) was designed to help students transition into university life, enhance their participation in student life, boost academic performance, and, increase student retention rates. The program centres on three S's: success, skills, and socialising, all providing a supportive and structured environment in the first year at college. Activities include new student orientation, developmental/college success courses, student academic advising/mentoring, peer-mentoring, workshops [9], student experience enhancing activities [8], academic trips [15] and FYE Graduation.

Students are formed into living/learning communities in which they take the same classes [7] and are assigned their own FYE advisor who meets with advisees regularly. In the student dormitory, the communities are assigned to one floor with an upper-level student serving as their resident assistant. In 2016 a new course called ENGR110 was introduced to further assist students in their transition to college.

1.3 An overview of the ENGR110 course

ENGR110 is a first-year course designed to help first-semester engineering students decide which major within the college is best for them, and prepare them for success at the college and beyond by teaching them important skills including engineering problem solving, ethical decision-making, and teamwork using active learning methods. This course enables students to gain a broad understanding and appreciation of the engineering profession, to become members of a learning community, and to become practised at the pathways to academic success in engineering studies.

The ENGR110 curriculum also incorporates structured departmental visits at all the engineering disciplines offered by the College of Engineering. These visits include a short introductory lecture followed by laboratory tours and hands-on activities to provide the students with practical examples of what they could expect should they

decide to pursue that particular major. Additionally, each department provides alumni to speak to interested students and to answer questions and concerns.

The learning outcomes for the course include:

- (1) a basic understanding of engineering problem-solving process and skills;
- (2) a broad understanding of the impacts of engineering and the petroleum industry in a global and societal context;
- (3) effective communication through reading, writing, listening and speaking;
- (4) encourage students to make an early and informed choice of major; and
- (5) an awareness of, and engagement in, independent study and life-long learning.

2 METHODOLOGY

Two surveys were conducted as part of this study. The first one (N=183) was a general questionnaire, with the aim of collecting background information about students' choices regarding majors, as well as contextual data on the students' soft-skills, including time management, setting academic goals, team-working skills, use of campus resources, and motivation for studying engineering. A follow-up survey was conducted on the same cohort five months later (N=153) to evaluate any variances in choices of majors and soft-skill improvements. Some specific questions from the first survey were discreetly repeated as part of the follow-up survey to equate results. The results of the course outcomes assessment done at the end of the course are also included.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Historically it has been found that approximately 30% of students attending the engineering college where the current study takes place formally changed their engineering major at least once during their studies. Figure 1 shows that in 2012 almost a quarter of the students changed their major. By 2015 this figure increased to almost one-third of the student body with little sign of any improvement in the situation.

Fig. 1. Students who changed their major after three semesters (Source: Office of the Registrar, PI)

Anecdotal evidence reveals that the most common reason was due to the student's limited knowledge of the true nature and the academic requirements needed in their chosen engineering major [6]. They had very likely made their initial choices mainly based on the advice, or pressure from an 'influencer' in their lives, be that a relative, friend or teacher. Addressing this issue, as well as the problem of student retention was the main driver for introducing the ENGR110 course described above.

3.1 Choosing a major

The authors are of the opinion that a lack-of-knowledge [6], lack-of-(soft)skills [9, 15], and/or lack-of-belonging within a specific discipline [2] may be contributing factors for switching majors (or even drop out) at a later stage. It appears that the data from the survey (Figure 2) support this, as double the amount of students (13.7%) queried their original decision compared to only 6.7% prior to starting the course. This notion of uncertainty is viewed as a significant positive, suggesting that introducing the students to the different engineering disciplines as part of their first-year experience might indeed result in making major-switching decisions during this period, instead of at a later date.

Fig. 2. Choice of majors prior to ENGR110 vs. choice of majors after introducing students to the different engineering disciplines (CE denotes Chemical; EE: Electrical; ME: Mechanical; PE: Petroleum and PGS: Petroleum Geosciences)

As the ENGR110 course is designed with hands-on engineering problem-solving skills, it aims to show students how technical problem-solving applies in practice. It also lets them demonstrate it through activities. It is essential that students develop the ability to identify with their specific engineering discipline at an early stage to secure a sense that they belong to that undergraduate peer group, a key ingredient of retention. It is why we also consider that the introduction to the Engineering disciplines plays an integral part in the efficacious declaration of their majors.

3.2 Course elements assisting in learning

Figure 3 below shows the student responses of the different course elements/activities that they felt assisted them most in their ENGR110 learning experience. It is evident that students consider the Introduction to Engineering disciplines (including the departmental visits) as most helpful, where most students (94%) 'agree' or 'strongly agree' with the concept, as this is most likely to assist them in their choice of majors, as discussed above. It is followed by field trips (75%), the studio/LAB sessions (71%), course lectures (68%) and lastly teamwork and class discussions (68%).

Fig. 3. Course elements/activities that students agreed or strongly agreed assisted most in ENGR110

Compulsory field trips in the curriculum for ENGR110 are intended to provide for more ‘student centred’ and ‘active learning’ activities and also to provide students with a realistic industry-related experience that is external to the classroom and university campus. Through direct experiential learning, it is hoped that the students will begin to ‘feel’ and ‘think’ like engineers and that they will observe that the topics and issues that are discussed in the classroom are also being applied and addressed in the professional world.

As an example, the initial group of ENGR110 students spent a full day at an oil industry conference and exhibition, one of the largest held annually in the world. They were assigned into small teams prior to the trip and were tasked on the day with taking a journalistic approach to the visit by interviewing many of the representative companies in the exhibition to gauge a feeling for “where the jobs are, and what are the desired skills for graduates today and in the future”. Assessment of the exercise required that each team later discuss and compare the results of their interviews and to submit a report summarising the main points while highlighting any emerging trends, similarities and anomalies between companies that they picked up on. Other field trips planned for the course includes visits to various engineering company’s manufacturing centres, research lab’s and technical offices in the area. Field trips form an essential element in the overall course objectives by reinforcing for students the themes of the course learning outcomes listed above.

3.3 Review of skills gained at the end of the course

The follow-up survey, five months later, was done to determine the effectiveness and longevity of FYE/ENGR110 programs and activities. Figure 4 below shows the results. It is evident from Figure 4 that students continued to reflect well on the personal and study skills gained, with very similar responses for key skills as when first surveyed at the start of the ENGR110 course.

Fig. 4. A comparison of responses at the start and the end of the course about usefulness of skills gained

3.4 Assessment of course outcomes

A standard survey regarding the success of the course outcomes showed that the instruction and assessment methods overall have been effective. However, the lowest achievement level was scored for the second Performance Indicator. This may indicate that the time that students spend on their individual department visits might not be adequate. One suggested improvement for this SLO might be the inclusion of an additional assignment relating to each of the engineering majors, instead of just using a short-answer or multiple-choice quiz.

4 CONCLUSION

Even with an improved and a more tailored course (e.g. ENGR110), careful attention needs to be paid early on to those students with an inability to identify with a specific engineering discipline. Despite evidence of a value-added curriculum (including academic advising), more can be done to enhance the undergraduate engineering experience in ways to ensure that students make informed and confident selections of majors early on in their course so that major-switching decisions occur during the first semester, rather than a few semesters down the line. The findings of this study must be considered as preliminary, and we recommend that the cohort is surveyed after each academic semester to confirm the effectiveness of the First Year Experience program and the ENGR110 course.

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